

Exploring the Usage of AI Tools in Education: Insights from Gen Z Undergraduates in Sri Lanka

Nimshiya Nishshanka^{1*}, Navodika Karunarathna², Nirmani Dayapathirana³, Rashmika Vidushan Karunarathna⁴, Hiran Kavinda Hewage⁵, Pabodi Anthony⁶,

1. SLIIT Business School, Sri Lanka Institute of Information Technology (SLIIT), Sri Lanka
ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0004-8796-567X>
2. SLIIT Business School, Sri Lanka Institute of Information Technology (SLIIT), Sri Lanka
ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4623-8319>
3. SLIIT Business School, Sri Lanka Institute of Information Technology (SLIIT), Sri Lanka
ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0001-2906-7677>
4. SLIIT Business School, Sri Lanka Institute of Information Technology (SLIIT), Sri Lanka
ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0005-8856-7400>
5. SLIIT Business School, Sri Lanka Institute of Information Technology (SLIIT), Sri Lanka
ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0009-2415-0680>
6. SLIIT Business School, Sri Lanka Institute of Information Technology (SLIIT), Sri Lanka
ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0002-6257-2437>

* Corresponding Author Email: bm21526398@my.sliit.lk

Abstract

Background: This study investigates the patterns of use and adoption of AI tools in Sri Lanka, with a special emphasis on Generation Z undergraduates who will enter the industry next. As AI is an emerging technology, how this generation interacts with and enriches knowledge through AI tools becomes a vital area of concern.

Objective: To identify key subjective factors influencing the adoption and usage of AI tools in education among Gen Z undergraduates in Sri Lanka.

Methodology: This study employs qualitative research methods, specifically semi-structured interviews, to gather insights from 18 university students across various disciplines. Thematic analysis was used to identify recurring themes related to undergraduates' subjective experiences, benefits received, and attitudes, for which MAXQDA is used as the analytical software.

Results: The findings demonstrate four key subjective factors that influence adoption and usage, such as academic work, awareness and adoption, challenges and risk, and helpful and supportive factors. The frequently used AI tool in Sri Lanka was noted as ChatGPT, which showed a high usage pattern in the analysis.

Conclusion: Understanding the usage patterns and adoption factors helps the community use AI tools effectively, as it makes them aware of the risks and helpful factors. Also, the facilities that

aid in adopting these AI tools could elevate the efficiency of their usage by making many students, future undergraduates, AI developers, and educational institutions aware of its benefits.

Unique Contribution: This research provides insights for future research by helping to understand the usage of emerging AI tools among Gen Z undergraduates in a developing country like Sri Lanka. The findings can be applied to understanding different generations and emerging generations, such as Generation Alpha.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence (AI), Gen Z, Undergraduates, AI Tools, Education.

Introduction

The arrival of deep learning in 2012 and the release of ChatGPT in 2022 sparked the urge to incorporate AI into the traditional tasks conducted worldwide, notably used to educate themselves (Albayati, 2024). User acceptance, social influence on user decision, the ability of the user to operate and understand AI Tools, availability of conditions which can facilitate in using the AI Tools like the affordability and availability of technology and the benefits received using AI Tools have caused in paving the way to adopt these tools in education (Ajzen, 1991; Sohn & Kwon, 2020; Taylor & Todd, 1995; Vecchiarini & Somià, 2023). AI technologies, including machine learning algorithms, natural language processing, and neural networks, can potentially support personalised learning experiences, automate routine tasks, and provide data-driven insights for both educators and students (Jain et al., 2024). For example, intelligent tutoring systems can provide learners instant feedback and individualised exercises while making the learning process more interactive and engaging (Crompton & Burke, 2023). User acceptance of ChatGPT as a daily used tool and to understand the changing stages of user knowledge and familiarity. Allowing decision-making to create benefits and avoid the challenges of implementing ChatGPT as a tool of artificial intelligence in an educational arena was stated by Albayati (2024). It has also been illustrated that writing skills, self-assurance, creativity, and understanding of academic ethics are required in using AI tools in academic work. Moreover, Do translator /Google Translate, Chat GPT3,5/ChatGPT4, and Grammarly were preferred by the students in their academics (Malik et al., 2023). Melnikovas (2018) specifies the importance of collecting subjective data such as ideas and experiences towards a phenomenon that could eradicate the limitation of using only quantitative data. Most of the studies conducted in Sri Lanka are related to online learning. The interaction of AI Tools and education among Gen Z undergraduates is an underexplored area, whose childhood was interwoven with technology and likely to embrace digital solutions in different aspects, including education, and employment. It is crucial to understand the impact of actual usage of AI tools through the current analysis to predict future usage and its effect on the country's development. The current study analyses how AI tools could be effectively used in education to eradicate the factors which lessen its positive impact.

1. Identify the subjective ideas and suggest novel factors that affect Sri Lankan Gen Z undergraduates to utilize AI tools in education.
2. Identifying usage patterns of different AI Tools among Sri Lankan Gen Z undergraduates to utilize AI tools in education.

Literature Review

Cultural and Socioeconomic Influences on AI Adoption

Cultural and socioeconomic factors significantly affect the adoption of Artificial Intelligence (AI) tools in education, particularly among Sri Lankan Gen Z undergraduates (Agyare et al., 2025). This demographic is characterised by a unique mix of values in cultures, social influence, familiarity with technology, and different socioeconomic backgrounds, all of which play a crucial role in shaping attitudes toward AI technologies (Ivanov et al., 2024). Research has shown that students with challenged socio-economic backgrounds frequently encounter difficulties in accessing technology, which can obstruct their ability to use AI tools effectively. For instance, limited access to reliable internet and modern devices can build disparities in education opportunities, leading to a digital divide that may immensely affect underprivileged students (El Yaman et al., 2023). Furthermore, educational achievement and socioeconomic status are closely linked; Thus, students with privileged socioeconomic backgrounds typically have greater familiarity and exposure to technology and favourable attitudes toward adopting AI tools in education. This disparity may aggravate the existing inequalities in educational outcomes, as students with limited access to AI tools may struggle to keep up with their peers with no limitations in accessing the technology (Valdez et al., 2023).

Self-Efficacy and Attitudes towards AI Tools

Self-efficacy and attitudes have a reciprocal relationship that needs to be investigated in relation to the usage of Artificial Intelligence (AI) tools, specifically in the context of education. Self-efficacy is defined as the belief in the individual's ability to perform a specific task effectively. This is a strong predictor that shapes how students perceive and engage AI technologies in education. Attitudes are shaped through the individual's favorability and unfavorability to a specific object (Ajzen, 1991). This significantly influences students' attitudes, indicating that students who believe in their ability to use technology are likely to embrace it in their education and learning processes (Wang et al., 2025).

The Role of AI in Enhancing Learning Experiences

AI tools enhance the personalised learning approach towards self-paced learning with tailored feedback and comfort. For example, intelligent tutoring systems (ITS) utilise AI algorithms to assess students' understanding and adapt instructional materials (Wei Cao, 2020). This instant feedback removes the frustration and boredom arising from traditional learning patterns and environments. Furthermore, leveraging AI in learning pathways can optimise learning experiences and understanding of complex concepts. AI technology contributes to exploring concepts, memorising, and improving critical thinking and problem-solving skills through realistic scenarios descriptively documented in educational literature (Vieriu & Petrea, 2025).

Challenges in AI Adoption

One of the main ethical concerns surrounding AI in education is data privacy and user trust. Therefore, ethical implications must be set to provide necessary guidelines to prevent harm to individual users (Jobin et al., 2019; Biagini, 2025). Academic dishonesty is one of the major challenges that arise with the adoption of AI in education, and it needs to be mitigated. It has also identified ethical issues such as plagiarism generation and incorrect information (Livberber &

Ayvaz, 2023). In addition, reservations have emerged due to possible over-reliance on these tools (Chan & Lee, 2023).

Methodology

Research Design

The study incorporated a qualitative research design to explore the actual usage of emerging AI Tools in education. The transition from online learning to AI Tools in Sri Lankan education demands an in-depth investigation, engaging the subjective ideas of the Generation Z undergraduate population studying in state universities and higher education institutions in Sri Lanka.

Sampling and Data Collection

The study used purposive sampling to select the participants among Generation Z undergraduates. The data collection was done through semi-structured interviews in November 2024, with a selected age group among the selected universities and institutions. The interview questions were developed using the existing literature and the insights of the quantitative study conducted. Eighteen participants were interviewed, fulfilling the data saturation requirements for the sample size from private institutions and state universities (Franzosi et al., 2013; Mathis et al., 2024).

Data Analysis

The data gathered through 18 interviews using the MAXQDA software was analysed using thematic analysis. In the first phase, the collected data was analyzed using selected quotations that occurred several times, and keywords were allocated to them. 62 codes were generated and categorized under five themes. One theme explains the usage pattern of AI Tools in Sri Lanka.

Data Collection

Demographic information of the 18 participants who completed the study is shown in Table 1

Table 1 Demographic Information of Respondents

<i>Respondent Letter</i>	<i>Gender</i>	<i>Age Group</i>	<i>Year of Study</i>	<i>Major</i>
<i>Participant A</i>	Female	18-22	Second Year	Economics and Social Science
<i>Participant B</i>	Male	18-22	Final Year	Software Engineering
<i>Participant C</i>	Female	23-26	Third Year	Physical Science
<i>Participant D</i>	Female	18-22	First Year	Engineering
<i>Participant E</i>	Male	23-26	Fourth Year	Agricultural Technology
<i>Participant F</i>	Female	18-22	Second Year	Management
<i>Participant G</i>	Male	18-22	First Year	Science
<i>Participant H</i>	Male	23-26	Second Year	Business Management
<i>Participant I</i>	Male	18-22	Second Year	Business Management

<i>Participant J</i>	Female	23-26	Third Year	Business Management
<i>Participant K</i>	Female	18-22	Second Year	Computer Science
<i>Participant L</i>	Male	23-26	Fourth Year	Business Management
<i>Participant M</i>	Male	18-22	First Year	Medicine
<i>Participant N</i>	Female	18-22	Third Year	Engineering
<i>Participant O</i>	Male	18-22	First Year	Full Stack Software Engineering
<i>Participant P</i>	Male	18-22	First Year	Software Engineering
<i>Participant Q</i>	Male	18-22	First Year	Software Engineering
<i>Participant R</i>	Male	18-22	First Year	Software Engineering

Results

1. Identify the subjective ideas and suggest novel factors that affect Sri Lankan Gen Z undergraduates to utilize AI tools in education

Awareness and Adoption Factors

Table 2 below illustrates the codes under the theme awareness and adoption factors under each segment and percentages.

Table 2 Awareness and Adoption Factor Percentage

<i>Codes</i>	<i>Segments</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
<i>Easy accessibility</i>	20	18.35%
<i>Own ability</i>	16	14.68%
<i>Influence of peers</i>	13	11.93%
<i>Influence of seniors</i>	13	11.93%
<i>Availability of technology</i>	10	9.17%
<i>Intelligent Software</i>	10	9.17%
<i>Affordability</i>	9	8.26%
<i>Imitates Human Intelligence</i>	9	8.26%
<i>Reliable internet</i>	7	6.42%
<i>Social Media</i>	2	1.83%
<i>Total</i>	109	100%

Many participants have mentioned their ideas on the awareness and adoption of these AI Tools. This theme captures the factors affecting the acceptance and usage of AI tools in their education as undergraduates in Sri Lanka. Out of the 10 codes identified under the theme of awareness and adoption factors, “Easy accessibility” and “Own Ability” take a higher percentage in influencing this theme. Easy accessibility primarily describes the ease of use, user-friendliness. Participant O: “When you are doing your assignment, it is easier to search for the necessary information using ChatGPT than searching through Google because ChatGPT searches for the necessary information through Google. They give us the facts about Google through their AI tools.” “I can

use any software if it is user-friendly. Nowadays most of the software is user friendly; so, the use is easy and understandable.” Participant B: “Accessibility of these tools also encourages me to incorporate them into my daily study routine.” Respondent E: “I find them very convenient because I can access them on my laptop or phone.” Respondent O claimed, “I gained the ability to use these tools for my university education due to my knowledge of technology.

Figure 1: Code Cloud - Awareness and Adoption Theme

Figure 2 above illustrates the code cloud to showcase the highest and the lowest generated codes.

Helpful and Supportive Factor

<i>Codes</i>	<i>Segments</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
<i>Time Saving and Less Effort</i>	23	24.47%
<i>Language and Writing Assistance</i>	16	17.02%
<i>Efficient and Quick Responses</i>	12	12.77%
<i>Understand complex and unknown facts</i>	11	11.70%
<i>Additional Ideas and Information</i>	9	9.57%
<i>Paraphrasing and summarizing</i>	8	8.51%
<i>Accurate and Relevant Information</i>	4	4.26%
<i>Organized and improved productivity</i>	3	3.19%
<i>Double Check Work</i>	2	2.13%
<i>Learning Tool</i>	1	1.06%
<i>Less Stressed</i>	1	1.06%
<i>Plagiarism Checked</i>	1	1.06%
<i>Tips for Education</i>	1	1.06%
<i>Translates</i>	1	1.06%
<i>creative content</i>	1	1.06%
<i>Total</i>	94	100%

Table 2 Helpful and Supportive Factors

Table 3 above illustrates the codes under the theme of helpful and supportive factors with each segment number and percentages.

The above table discusses the codes under the theme “Helpful and Supportive Factors”. This emphasizes the theme that has led the Gen Z undergraduates of Sri Lanka to adopt and use AI Tools in their educational work. 24.47% of the influence is created by the code “Times Saving and Less Effort,” showcasing as the highest influencing code in the theme. As per this frequency, Gen Z undergraduates use these AI Tools because they save their time and reduce the effort needed. Participant Q “*You can save time by using an AI tool. If we Google it while looking for an answer to a problem, we must go to Wikipedia to find it. When using an AI tool, when the title and the facts are entered, it considers every available information to find answers to the questions which saves time.*” Participant O: “*Managing time has become easier.*” Generation Z undergraduates can save time for the work that require an overwhelming amount of attention, but once they utilise AI Tools for the work, it consumes lesser attention and effort. “Language and Writing assistance” code takes the second highest percentage, which influences the theme “Helpful and Supportive Factors”. Participant A stated, “*It Improves my vocabulary*”, and Participant P commented, “*Grammar is checked*”. For instance, Participant E commented that “*The speed at which AI tools generate answers and suggestions is a big advantage*” and Respondent O has mentioned “*Because we want to do the project better, we use AI tools at that time when we come to a situation where we get stuck. After doing that, the necessary areas will be resolved. We got a project a few days ago to create a desktop application. Then in doing the additional parts that we didn't know, we found a lot of codes that we were ignorant of, so we used AI Tools because they were needed for such things.*” As per the participants' answers, it is noted that AI Tools are significantly adapted due to the presence of helpful and supportive factors, such as getting to know the unknown and complex facts and their efficiency by the Gen Z undergraduates in Sri Lanka. “Paraphrasing and summarising”, “Accurate and Relevant Information”, “Organized and improved productivity”, “Double Check Work”, “Learning Tool”, “Less Stressfulness”, “Plagiarism Checking”, “Tips for

Education”, “Translation”, “creative content” were the other codes that contributed to the theme with low percentages in comparison to the codes with higher percentages.

Figure 2: Code Cloud - Helpful and Supportive Theme.

Figure 3 above illustrates the code cloud to show the major and minor codes affecting the theme's helpful and supportive factor.

Academic Work Theme

Participant O: “When it comes to project work, lecturers at the university request us to engage in self-studies in addition to the lecture content.” The participant explained that AI tools are used to

create study plans, as per the guidance of university superiors. Participant E commented: “AI tools help to organize study schedules and set reminders for exams.” Hence, personalized study plans have been created with the assistance of AI Tools. Participant P stated, “I tools help us verify whether an answer is right or wrong.” Thus, Participant P illustrates that AI Tools are used to check the accuracy of an assignment, and to check the content accuracy which allows self-assessment of an individual work. “You can do your assignments quickly and easily. I use these tools mainly to illicit the main points I must include in my assignment and to understand the assignment requirements in a short time.” Therefore, participant H explains that AI Tools are used as helping tools to do their assignment, not to do the entire assignment alone. 7.41% out of the identified segments under the theme “Academic Work” have used AI Tools in “Presentation Creation”, “Reference Check”, and “drafting and answering academic work” whereas the least influence was created towards the academic work with IT-related creations, and revision notes.

Figure 3: Code Cloud - Academic Work Theme

Figure 4 above explains the code percentages of the academic work factors faced by Gen Z undergraduates in Sri Lanka.

Challenges and Risk Factors

Figure 4: Percentages of Challenges and Risk Factors

Figure 5 above explains the code percentages of the challenges and risks faced by Gen Z undergraduates in Sri Lanka.

Challenges and Risk Factors theme depicts the hardships faced by the AI Tool users. These factors hinder the effective usage of AI Tools by Gen Z undergraduates in Sri Lanka. Each of these percentages showcases how frequently the respondents mentioned these challenges and risk factors. The highest challenge with the usage and adoption of AI Tools is recorded under the code

“Reduce creativity and thinking ability.” As per respondent H's statement, “*There are pros and cons of AI. So, I think if we search for something and Google it, we can get a lot of knowledge in addition to that. But since we can get information quickly, we don't care much about that additional information. That's the bad side.*” This statement suggests that AI Tool usage reduces effort and rational thinking to think beyond the content that is generated. Respondent R stated, “*I feel that I may lose my skills and thinking ability.*” Respondent G stated, “*The brain function often decreases because we are not motivated to think.*” Respondent A commented, “*Also, there are instances when I feel an over-dependency on AI which could affect my critical thinking or creativity.*” Thus, there is a probability of losing one’s skills, creativity, and critical thinking ability due to an over-dependence on AI tools such an addition could lead to diverse effects. The next challenge that was frequently repeated by respondents was the generation of “Inaccurate and Irrelevant Information.” Respondent G mentioned, “*When data was obtained about something, necessary as well as irrelevant data are often generated.*” Thus, AI tools generate unimportant information for the search prompt given. The respondents need to be careful with the text generated or information. It needs to be rechecked by the user to clarify the validity of the data which may sometimes be a time-consuming effort.

2. Identifying usage patterns of different AI Tools among Sri Lankan Gen Z undergraduates to utilize AI tools in education.

Frequently used AI Tools

Figure 5: Usage Pattern - Frequently Used AI tools in Sri Lanka

Figure 6 above illustrates the code percentages generated according to the theme of frequently used AI tools by the Gen Z undergraduates in Sri Lanka.

According to the bar graph, which depicts the frequency of using various AI Tools, ChatGPT has the highest frequency of use among AI Tools, with other tools' usage recorded as 34%. Secondly, 21% of users frequently used Gemini, and Quill Bot was recorded as the third most frequent user (14%). Grammarly(7%), Black Box AI(4%), and Co-pilot (4%) have a slightly elevated usage compared to the least used AI Tools such as Canva (2%), Capital AI (2%), Cram (2%), Jasper (2%), Khan Academy’s AI (2%), Leonardo AI (2%), Sigma AI (2%), Socratic (2%), and Zoom’s transcription feature (2%). Participant F stated: “*ChatGPT can help with assignments, and I’ve*

seen many of the undergraduates using it to generate ideas and outline their work quickly.” Participant F claimed: “I use QuillBot for paraphrasing and improving my writing and checking plagiarism which its new feature is quite useful.” Participant P: “Black box AI is very useful in programming.” Therefore, it is evident that many undergraduates use AI Tools based on the needs of the users as shown through the comments given above.

Figure 6 Themes affecting Actual Usage

Figure 7: Illustrates the themes affecting actual usage denoted by the study results.

Discussion

According to the results, AI Tools are primarily used by Gen Z undergraduates in Sri Lanka to generate personalised study plans. The participants revealed that AI tools correctly interpret a prompt's wording, provide faster access to information, increase students' efficiency and productivity, and help generate new ideas, which confirms a previous study's finding (Vecchiarini & Somià, 2023). As per respondent R's statement, “I feel that I may lose my skills, and thinking ability.”, where the respondent specifies the danger of losing one's creativity and critical thinking. Respondent O specified, “Sometimes, when developing a program, we can add additional parts by using AI tools. So, they say that using them at that time is okay.” This comment is related to the code of additional ideas and information in the current study, which also coincides with a finding of former research (Vecchiarini & Somià, 2023).

Moreover, challenges and risk factors of using AI tools in education were investigated in the study. These AI tools were found to generate inaccurate and irrelevant information. According to respondent I: “These sometimes give incorrect or incomplete information, and I have to counter-check for their accuracy.” Even though AI Tools are typically beneficial, they may have certain risks. Gen Z undergraduates illustrate that it is necessary to identify the risk factors involved in an attempt to eliminate them, specifically, by checking for the accuracy of information and being aware of the generation of irrelevant and inaccurate information. This complies with one of the studies (Vecchiarini & Somià, 2023). In general, the present study's data complies with the findings of many previous work; however, there are some distinctive findings as well. For example, though students in this study found that AI assists in language learning, Shen et al. (2023) state that overusing AI may weaken one's creativity and problem-solving skills. Some of the participants in

this study also shared this concern as an implication of relying heavily on AI tools. Furthermore, the overall culture of accepting AI in the Sri Lankan context, differs from the studies emerging from supposedly more technologically developing countries, where the acceptance of AI is reported to be significantly higher (Hua, 2023). Social influence is stated as a major factor that affects intention. The study presents the importance of peers, senior influence and social media in adopting and making users aware of AI Tools in education. According to Ajzen (1991), the attitude of the user affects the adoption of AI Tools, whereas the current study reveals subjective ideas on the actual usage of AI Tools among Gen Z undergraduates in Sri Lanka. The tendency to use AI Tools due to their helpful and supportive aspect and being helpful in academic work. Favourability and unfavourability affect the attitude of the user (Almaraz-López et al., 2023). The study presents challenges and risk factors of AI Tool usage in education, specifying recommendations that must be avoided when using AI Tools. The frequency of usage of different AI Tools depicts different considerations of Gen Z undergraduates in Sri Lanka. ChatGPT stands as the most frequently used AI Tool among Gen Z undergraduates in Sri Lanka, competing with the study of (Albayati, 2024). Further, unique usage patterns were identified in the current study, such as using Grammarly to improve vocabulary and grammar. Moreover, ChatGPT, Quillbot, and Gemini assist Gen Z undergraduates in maintaining the accuracy of their writing by generating effective ideas, creating content, and refining the writing. Thus, the undergraduates can improve their language skills, vocabulary, and writing. Also, Blackbox AI and Capital AI can aid programming-related education. Undergraduates can use the feature of transcribing in Zoom for research purposes and the academic education needed in transcribing. This study shows unique results compared to the results generated in the study of Malik et al. (2023). Awareness among AI tool users suggests that it is vital to have a good internet connection, technological equipment, affordability, and the ability to use these tools, suggesting unique results concerning the study of (Ajzen, 1991; Pan, 2020). Identification of the subjective ideas generated under each theme of this study uplifts the understanding of AI usage in Sri Lanka, helping to achieve the National AI Strategy in 2030 (Artificial Intelligence in Sri Lanka ", 2024). Anuradha Choudhary (2023) specifies the positive contributions of AI technology to the users. Similarly, the study focuses on the helpful and supportive factors that explain the effectiveness of AI Tools use in the education sector.

Conclusion

The research explores the actual usage of AI Tools by Gen Z undergraduates in Sri Lanka. As a developing country, Sri Lanka should stay abreast of the new developments in the world, such as AI technology. Therefore, Sri Lanka needs to stay relevant by reducing the digital divide and incorporating AI technology. Under the ranking of Oxford Insights' 2023 Government AI Readiness Index, Sri Lanka is placed at 95th out of 193 countries. Therefore, it is crucial to evaluate the actual usage of AI in Sri Lanka to maintain competitiveness with the world's AI readiness. The study specifies these ideas using the insights of Gen Z undergraduates, who are an emerging generation born with technology and who are about to interact with the industry. Undergraduate education is crucial as it affects the long-term continuity of a country. Therefore, this study investigates the subjective ideas of Gen Z undergraduates and acknowledges how AI Tools have influenced their education. The subjective ideas show their attitudes, perceptions, and the factors causing for adoption of AI Tools in education. This study shows the usage patterns of different AI Tools and the level of engagement with AI Tools in education. This study encourages young undergraduates all AI users in general, and specifically the AI developers to form policies and

upgrades by understanding subjective ideas. Furthermore, the National AI Centre could incorporate the findings of this study in analyzing the AI integration towards education. Further studies can focus on the impact of AI instruments on the student's performance and academic achievements. Future studies can focus also on the use of AI tools with, other age groups, geographical locations, and levels of education to complement the results obtained for the group of Gen Z undergraduates.

References

- Agyare, B., Asare, J., Kraishan, A., Nkrumah, I., & Adjekum, D. K. (2025). A cross-national assessment of artificial intelligence (AI) Chatbot user perceptions in collegiate physics education. *Computers and Education: Artificial Intelligence*, 8, 100365. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.caeai.2025.100365>
- Ajzen, I. (1991). The Theory of Planned Behavior. *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes*, 50, 179-211. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0749-5978\(91\)90020-T](https://doi.org/10.1016/0749-5978(91)90020-T)
- Albayati, H. (2024). Investigating undergraduate students' perceptions and awareness of using ChatGPT as a regular assistance tool: A user acceptance perspective study. *Computers and Education: Artificial Intelligence*, 6, 100203. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.caeai.2024.100203>
- Almaraz-López, C., Almaraz-Menendez, F., & Lopez, C. (2023). Comparative Study of the Attitudes and Perceptions of University Students in Business Administration and Management and in Education toward Artificial Intelligence. *Education Sciences*, 13, 609. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci13060609>
- Anuradha Choudhary, A. N. C. (2023). The Transformative Role of Artificial Intelligence in Training Obstetrics and Gynecology Residents. <https://doi.org/10.5005/jp-journals-11012-0012>
- Artificial Intelligence in Sri Lanka (2024). White Paper developed by the Committee on Formulating a Strategy for Artificial Intelligence (CFSAI) <https://mot.gov.lk/assets/files/AI%20White%20Paper%20March%202024-c09aa49f7990358ad1442103b804511d.pdf>
- Chan, C., & Lee, K. (2023). *The AI generation gap: Are Gen Z students more interested in adopting generative AI such as ChatGPT in teaching and learning than their Gen X and Millennial Generation teachers?* <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2305.02878>
- Biagini, G. (2025). Towards an AI-Literate Future: A Systematic Literature Review Exploring Education, Ethics, and Applications. *International Journal of Artificial Intelligence in Education*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40593-025-00466-w>
- Crompton, H., & Burke, D. (2023). Artificial intelligence in higher education: the state of the field. *International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education*, 20. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41239-023-00392-8>
- El Yaman, N., Zeitoun, J., Diab, R., Mdaihly, M., Diab, R., Kobeissi, L., Ljoud, S., Antoun, J., & Bardus, M. (2023). Utilization of patient portals: a cross-sectional study investigating associations with mobile app quality. *BMC Medical Informatics and Decision Making*, 23. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12911-023-02252-x>

- Franzosi, R., Doyle, S., McClelland, L. E., Putnam Rankin, C., & Vicari, S. (2013). Quantitative narrative analysis software options compared: PC-ACE and CAQDAS (ATLAS.ti, MAXqda, and NVivo). *Quality & Quantity*, 47(6), 3219-3247. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11135-012-9714-3>
- Hua, J. (2023). Beyond Exams: Investigating AI Tool Impact on Student Attitudes, Ethical Awareness, and Academic Dishonesty in Online College Assessments. *International Journal of Educational Management and Development Studies*, 4(4), 160-185. <https://doi.org/10.53378/353030>
- Ivanov, S., Soliman, M., Tuomi, A., Nasser Alhamar Alkathiri, & Al-Alawi, A. N. (2024). Drivers of generative AI adoption in higher education through the lens of the theory of planned behaviour. *Technology in Society*, 77, 102521–102521. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techsoc.2024.102521>
- Jain, K., Naga, J., & Raghuram, V. (2024). Unlocking potential: The impact of AI on education technology. *Multidisciplinary Reviews*, 7, 2024049. <https://doi.org/10.31893/multirev.2024049>
- Jobin, A., Ienca, M., & Vayena, E. (2019). The global landscape of AI ethics guidelines. *Nature Machine Intelligence*, 1. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s42256-019-0088-2>
- Livberber, T., & Ayvaz, S. (2023). The impact of Artificial Intelligence in academia: Views of Turkish academics on ChatGPT. *Heliyon*, 9(9), e19688. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e19688>
- Malik, A., Pratiwi, Y., Andajani, K., Numertayasa, I., Suharti, S., Darwis, A., & Marzuki. (2023). Exploring Artificial Intelligence in Academic Essay: Higher Education Student's Perspective. *International Journal of Educational Research Open*, 5, 100296. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijedro.2023.100296>
- Mathis, W. S., Zhao, S., Pratt, N., Weleff, J., & De Paoli, S. (2024). Inductive thematic analysis of healthcare qualitative interviews using open-source large language models: How does it compare to traditional methods? *Computer Methods and Programs in Biomedicine*, 255, 108356. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cmpb.2024.108356>
- Melnikovas, A. (2018). Towards an Explicit Research Methodology: Adapting Research Onion Model for Futures Studies. *Journal of Futures Studies*,. [https://doi.org/10.6531/JFS.201812_23\(2\).0003](https://doi.org/10.6531/JFS.201812_23(2).0003)
- Pan, X. (2020). Technology Acceptance, Technological Self-Efficacy, and Attitude Toward Technology-Based Self-Directed Learning: Learning Motivation as a Mediator. *Front Psychol*, 11, 564294. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2020.564294>
- Shen, Y., Heacock, L., Elias, J., Hentel, K., Reig, B., Shih, G., & Moy, L. (2023). ChatGPT and Other Large Language Models Are Double-Edged Swords. *Radiology*, 307. <https://doi.org/10.1148/radiol.230163>
- Sohn, K., & Kwon, O. (2020). Technology acceptance theories and factors influencing artificial intelligence-based intelligent products. *Telematics and Informatics*, 47, 101324. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tele.2019.101324>
- Taylor, S., & Todd, P. (1995). Decomposition and crossover effects in the theory of planned behavior: A study of consumer adoption intentions. *International Journal of Research in Marketing*, 12(2), 137-155. [https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/0167-8116\(94\)00019-K](https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/0167-8116(94)00019-K)
- Valdez, A., Amba, O., Jr, R., Dimalna, H., Gomampong, A., & Manaol, N. (2023). Farmers Perceptions on Artificial Insemination (AI): A Mixed Method Design. *European Journal*

E-ISSN: 2735-9891 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15505292>

- of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 1, 299-323.
[https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2023.1\(3\).31](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2023.1(3).31)
- Vecchiarini, M., & Somià, T. (2023). Redefining entrepreneurship education in the age of artificial intelligence: An explorative analysis. *The International Journal of Management Education*, 21(3), 100879. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijme.2023.100879>
- Vieriu, A. M., & Petrea, G. (2025). The Impact of Artificial Intelligence (AI) on Students' Academic Development. *Education Sciences*, 15(3), 343. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci15030343>
- Wang, K., Cui, W., & Yuan, X. (2025). Artificial Intelligence in Higher Education: The Impact of Need Satisfaction on Artificial Intelligence Literacy Mediated by Self-Regulated Learning Strategies. *Behavioral Sciences*, 15(2), 165. <https://doi.org/10.3390/bs15020165>
- Wei Cao, Q. W., Asma Sbeih, FHA. Shibly. (2020). Artificial Intelligence Based Efficient Smart Learning Framework for Education Platform>. *INTELIGENCIA ARTIFICIAL*, 23. <https://doi.org/https://dio.org/10.4114/intartf.vol20iss59pp123-127>